

Hydrogen May or May Not Be a Pure Fuel When Utilized in Substantial Quantities

Konstantinos T. Kotsis

*Lab of training and teaching of Physics, Department of Primary Education,
University of Ioannina, Greece*

Suggested Citation

Kotsis, K. T. (2024). Hydrogen may or may not be a pure fuel when utilized in substantial quantities. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(3), 760-767.

DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(3\).59](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(3).59)

Abstract:

A detailed analysis of the widespread use of hydrogen as a clean fuel is presented in this study. To properly address this issue, the research is organized into several parts that guide the investigation of important components. It is essential to have an introduction to provide the groundwork for comprehending the significance of hydrogen as a source of clean energy. From there, the research delves into the technical components of hydrogen fuel technology and the breakthroughs made in the transportation and industrial sectors. The last part of this presentation will consist of a critical analysis of the

environmental advantages and problems linked with the broad use of hydrogen fuel.

Keywords: *hydrogen, pure fuel, environment.*

Introduction

Considered a viable clean fuel alternative, hydrogen has drawn interest due to its potential use in many energy-related fields. A systems study of hydrogen as a vehicle for energy in the US confirmed its viability except for some transportation uses, emphasizing its use in the commercial, industrial, residential, and power production domains (Blank et al., 1973). Methods like thermochemical decomposition of water or coal conversion indicate economic feasibility, with predicted production prices ranging from \$1.00 to \$1.50 per million Btu (Gao et al., 2020). Large-scale transmission and storage systems must be developed to avoid hydrogen-induced embrittlement for broad deployment. These systems should resemble the current natural gas pipeline network (Ahad et al., 2022). In light of the current environment, the concept of using hydrogen as an aviation fuel source has been put up, highlighting factors such

as sustainability, fuel economy, and combustion in subsonic aircraft applications. Ultimately, including hydrogen as a clean energy source is consistent with societal norms and would work with the current energy structure (Falcone et al., 2021).

Transitioning to clean fuels, such as hydrogen, is pivotal in addressing pressing environmental concerns plaguing our current energy systems. As articulated in the literature (Jamashb et al., 2006), the reliance on conventional electricity sources poses environmental and security threats and necessitates a shift towards innovative technological solutions. The potential of hydrogen as an alternative energy source is increasingly recognized, with projections indicating its viability as a primary fuel for road vehicles (Dogger et al., 2009). Although there are recognized disadvantages and uncertainties associated with the use of hydrogen, the urgent need to reduce the harmful effects of fossil fuels

on public health and the environment justifies a comprehensive assessment of the advantages and disadvantages of transitioning to clean fuels such as hydrogen. This scrutiny is crucial in the nascent stages of hydrogen technology development to address knowledge gaps and shape strategic approaches towards sustainable energy transitions.

Examining the possible advantages and obstacles related to the extensive use of hydrogen fuel is essential for evaluating its purity on a large scale. The National Aerospace Plane's use of hydrogen fuel underscores this energy source's efficacy and environmental benefits, notably in the realm of air-breathing and space travel technology (Hannum et al., 1989). Moreover, the application of phosphoric acid fuel cells in various sectors, such as underground mine locomotives and railroad engines, underscores the versatility and promise of hydrogen fuel in reducing emissions and promoting sustainability (Stickles & Breuer, 1983). Through a careful analysis of these progressions and breakthroughs in hydrogen fuel technology, it becomes clear that the shift towards hydrogen may have a crucial impact in advocating for more widespread use of greener energy options. With the rising need for cleaner fuel options, the potential of hydrogen to contribute to a cleaner and more sustainable future is becoming more evident (Singla et al., 2021).

Drawing from Khan (2023), integrating Industry 4.0 technologies into the space industry parallels the innovative possibilities that hydrogen fuel presents. Additionally, including the abstract, as indicated in Soto (2021), will offer further insights into this complex topic, enhancing the discourse on the potential of hydrogen as a clean and sustainable energy solution for the future.

Environmental Benefits of Hydrogen Fuel

The widespread adoption of hydrogen as a clean fuel holds promise for achieving zero greenhouse gas emissions during combustion, as evidenced by research findings (Demuyne et al.,

2010). The assessment of hydrogen-powered internal combustion engines emphasizes the need for precise thermodynamic models for optimizing engine configurations, specifically in minimizing nitrogen oxide emissions (Manuel et al., 2024). However, challenges persist in accurately modeling heat transfer generated by hydrogen combustion, necessitating improvements in existing models. In transitioning to clean energy sources like hydrogen, strategic planning is crucial to address energy demand shifts and mitigate carbon emissions effectively (Walsh et al., 2019). Cities such as Boston may move towards carbon neutrality by prioritizing energy efficiency, electrifying building heating services, and increasing the power supply free of carbon emissions. This approach not only supports economic growth but also promotes environmental sustainability.

Urban areas are notorious for their high levels of air pollution, which pose serious health risks to residents. To combat this issue, reducing air pollution has become a key focus for policymakers and environmentalists alike (Neves et al., 2020). An effective approach is using clean fuels, such as hydrogen, extensively in many sectors and transportation networks. By shifting from conventional fossil fuels to hydrogen, the release of detrimental pollutants such as carbon dioxide and nitrogen oxides may be substantially reduced. Additionally, hydrogen fuel cells produce zero emissions when used, making them a sustainable and environmentally friendly option for urban areas struggling with air quality issues (Dawood et al., 2020). Introducing hydrogen as a clean fuel source can transform urban transit and industrial operations, leading to a more environmentally friendly and healthier future for urban residents. By using cutting-edge technology and implementing well-thought-out strategies, it is possible to reduce air pollution effectively and efficiently in metropolitan areas.

Mitigating climate change necessitates a multifaceted approach encompassing innovative solutions and comprehensive policies. As Terlouw et al. (2021) emphasized in their exploration of the long-term reversibility of CO₂ emissions, technologies such as direct air capture

offer promising avenues to limit the environmental impact of greenhouse gases. This aligns with the urgency highlighted in the analysis of traffic-related air pollution by Boogaard et al. (2022), emphasizing the detrimental effects on air quality and human health. By including both viewpoints, it becomes clear that successful methods for mitigating climate change must tackle emissions' origins and the regulatory systems that manage pollution. Hence, it is essential to adopt sustainable practices and enforce strict regulations based on scientific study and technical progress to effectively use hydrogen as an environmentally friendly fuel to address climate change worldwide.

As highlighted in recent research, the transition to sustainable energy production represents a pivotal shift in addressing the pressing challenges associated with fossil fuel dependency (Kabeyi & Olanrewaju, 2022). The potential of hydrogen as a clean fuel option for road vehicles, as outlined by the Dutch Energy Research Centre (Dogger et al., 2009), offers a promising avenue for reducing environmental impact and enhancing energy efficiency. This aligns with the urgent need for decarbonization emphasized in the Fourth National Climate Assessment and the IPCC Special Report (Arroyo et al., 2019), underscoring the critical importance of transitioning to low-carbon energy sources. By embracing hydrogen technologies and fostering a shift towards a hydrogen-based transportation system, greenhouse gas emissions can be curbed (Lebrouhi et al., 2022), and additional benefits such as improved public health, enhanced mobility options, and economic growth can be realized. The comprehensive strategy for producing sustainable energy has great promise for reducing the effects of climate change and progressing towards a more ecologically conscious future.

Challenges and Limitations of Hydrogen Fuel

Manufacturing processes for clean fuel production, particularly in the context of

hydrogen, face significant challenges due to high production costs and energy intensity. (Inayat et al., 2017) analyzing the economic feasibility of biomass steam gasification for hydrogen production from palm waste reveals promising prospects for cost optimization, indicating the potential for low production costs. Moreover, (Ali et al., 2017) explore the utilization of microalgae as a renewable feedstock for biodiesel production, highlighting its economic viability as an alternative to traditional fuels. These findings highlight the need to tackle the expensive manufacturing costs and energy-intensive procedures while shifting towards cleaner fuel options such as hydrogen. To achieve environmental and economic sustainability goals, the energy industry can overcome the challenges of expensive and energy-intensive manufacturing processes by optimizing operational parameters and using sustainable feedstocks like palm waste and microalgae. This will facilitate the widespread adoption of clean fuels.

The transition to a cleaner fuel source such as hydrogen faces significant challenges, one of which pertains to the limited infrastructure for hydrogen storage and distribution. As highlighted in (Walsh et al., 2019), developing sustainable energy sources is crucial in meeting carbon mitigation targets and ensuring economic development. To address this issue, innovative approaches like CO₂ recycling, as discussed in (Navarro et al., 2018), present opportunities to optimize energy efficiency and minimize emissions. Using hydrogen as a clean fuel may be boosted by implementing circular economy models and investigating advanced technologies such as structured reactors. However, effectively executing these methods requires overcoming infrastructure preparedness and operational effectiveness obstacles. It is crucial to enhance the hydrogen storage and distribution networks to facilitate the broad use of hydrogen as a clean energy alternative (Sikiru et al., 2024).

When examining the difficulties in expanding hydrogen production for general use as a clean fuel, it is essential to explore the technical obstacles hindering this transformation. The analysis of technological innovation systems (TIS), as outlined in (Hacking et al., 2019), sheds light on the intricate network of actors, institutions, and technologies crucial for fostering emerging energy technologies like hydrogen. Understanding the dynamics of cumulative causation within a TIS can provide strategic clues on accelerating the development of hydrogen production technologies. Furthermore, (Egenhofer et al., 2007) emphasize the importance of concrete steps in technology development, demonstration, and diffusion to enable a global track for post-2012 frameworks, suggesting a structured approach to tackling barriers. Combining knowledge from these investigations makes it clear that overcoming technical obstacles via collaborative efforts within TIS may accelerate the widespread adoption of hydrogen as a clean fuel, eventually leading to its extensive use.

Furthermore, it is essential to consider the safety implications associated with the storage and handling of hydrogen in the extensive use of this environmentally friendly fuel technology. Hydrogen is very combustible and requires careful handling to avoid mishaps or detonations. Improper management of hydrogen storage may be risky due to its tiny and lightweight nature, which makes it prone to easy leakage from containers. Additionally, the infrastructure for transporting and storing hydrogen must adhere to rigorous safety regulations to minimize the possible hazards of handling this highly volatile chemical (Moretto & Quong, 2021). Ongoing research is being conducted to solve safety issues and ensure the safe use of hydrogen as a clean energy source in several industries. This research focuses on enhanced storage materials and technologies. Nevertheless, it is crucial to maintain a state of alertness and implement regulatory actions to

protect against any dangers related to the storage and handling of hydrogen.

Potential Applications and Industries for Massive Hydrogen Use

The envisioned transition to hydrogen-powered vehicles, as outlined in the cited studies, requires a systemic shift that necessitates coordinated efforts from various stakeholders in the transportation sector (Hosseini, 2023). The obstacles associated with implementing fuel-cell automobiles and hydrogen-powered trains include scientific progress, establishing an all-encompassing fuel infrastructure, and adopting these technologies to consumers. Although the economic obstacles and initial expenses may seem challenging, the potential economic, ecological, and national security advantages are significant. To drive this transition effectively, sustained commitment and strategic policy incentives are indispensable (Qadir et al., 2021). The comprehensive analyses presented in the research underscore the importance of careful planning and collaboration among industry players, government agencies, and researchers to realize the potential of hydrogen as a clean fuel in transforming the transportation sector.

Industrial applications of hydrogen in manufacturing processes hold significant potential for reducing carbon emissions and advancing sustainable practices in the industry. The capabilities of Midlands-based organizations in hydrogen and fuel cell technologies, as highlighted in (Speers & Walsh, 2010), underscore the growing interest in leveraging hydrogen as a clean energy source within manufacturing settings. Moreover, assessing the state's potential for capturing heat generated during electricity production or industrial processes, as discussed in (Beiron et al., 2022), further emphasizes the importance of adopting innovative approaches like hydrogen utilization to meet thermal needs and cut fossil fuel use. Manufacturers may improve energy efficiency, lower emissions, and contribute to a greener industrial environment by addressing obstacles to adopting combined heat and power.

Adopting hydrogen in industrial processes aligns with sustainability objectives, provides economic benefits, and fosters technical advancement.

The integration of hydrogen technology plays a pivotal role in addressing energy storage challenges within renewable energy systems. As highlighted in (Egenhofer et al., 2007), technology development, demonstration, and diffusion are crucial elements for advancing a global technology track post-2012. This underscores the urgency of adopting hydrogen as a clean energy carrier to support renewable energy integration. Furthermore, (Speers and Walsh, 2010) emphasize the importance of regional collaborations, such as establishing a Midlands hydrogen cluster, to leverage hydrogen and fuel cell technologies capabilities. By capitalizing on these prospects for novelty and financial commitment, the shift towards a hydrogen-powered energy storage system may augment the total effectiveness and durability of incorporating renewable energy. Therefore, using hydrogen as a clean fuel is crucial to fully harness its immense potential in revolutionizing the energy sector towards a more environmentally friendly future.

Hydrogen for heating and power generation in residential and commercial settings holds immense potential for reducing carbon emissions and transitioning toward clean energy sources. In residential applications, hydrogen can be used in fuel cells to generate heat and electricity, offering a renewable and efficient alternative to traditional fossil fuels (Megia et al., 2021). In commercial buildings, hydrogen-powered heating systems can provide a sustainable solution for reducing greenhouse gas emissions and promoting environmental sustainability. According to Amin et al. (2022), the widespread adoption of hydrogen technologies for heating and power generation can significantly decrease carbon dioxide emissions and contribute to global efforts to combat climate change. Furthermore, (Iulianelli & Basile, 2014.) highlights the versatility of hydrogen as a clean fuel source, making it a promising option for a wide range of applications in both residential and commercial sectors.

Conclusion

The transition to hydrogen fuel holds significant promise in addressing environmental concerns, particularly in urban transportation. As global temperatures rise and concerns over CO₂ emissions intensify, the need for sustainable energy sources becomes paramount. Hydrogen-powered trams, as discussed in (Hassan et al., 2019), offer a compelling solution by reducing energy consumption and pollutant emissions in densely populated areas. Moreover, as outlined in (Egenhofer et al., 2007), developing a global technology track underscores the importance of innovation and investment in clean technologies like hydrogen fuel. By summarizing the positive environmental impacts of hydrogen fuel, such as its ability to reduce climate change, decrease pollution, and enhance energy efficiency, we may better understand its importance in the wider context of sustainable development and global decarbonization efforts.

Due to the many benefits of hydrogen as an environmentally friendly fuel, addressing the obstacles hindering its widespread use is imperative. An essential obstacle is establishing a robust infrastructure capable of effectively generating, storing, and disseminating hydrogen. Building resilient infrastructure requires substantial financial commitment and cooperation among governmental bodies, companies, and research organizations. In addition, it is imperative to decrease the cost of hydrogen generation to compete effectively with conventional fossil fuels. Exploration of cutting-edge technologies like electrolysis, biomass gasification, and renewable energy sources can potentially reduce expenses. Furthermore, it is essential to adopt legislation and policies that promote the development and utilization of hydrogen as a fuel to create an atmosphere favorable to growth. Using joint efforts, technical progress, and favorable regulations, it is possible to utilize hydrogen as an environmentally friendly fuel widely.

Furthermore, with the continuous progress of technology, the potential for hydrogen to be used as a large-scale clean fuel is becoming increasingly encouraging. Through continuous

research and development, advancements in hydrogen production, storage, and infrastructure are progressing quickly, positioning hydrogen as a viable choice for sustainable energy solutions. Moreover, the increasing emphasis on decreasing carbon emissions and the need to address climate change have positioned hydrogen as a central topic in conversations about clean energy. With governments globally pledging to achieve net-zero emissions, there will be a significant increase in the demand for environmentally friendly fuels such as hydrogen in the near future. The hydrogen technology sector is seeing a significant increase in investments, strengthening the industry and facilitating its wider acceptance. In conclusion, the trajectory for hydrogen as a clean fuel on a massive scale looks very optimistic, with the potential to revolutionize the energy landscape and contribute significantly to a more sustainable future (Romm, 2013).

In the context of a sustainable energy future, the role of hydrogen as a clean fuel source is increasingly gaining traction. As highlighted in the report (Walsh et al., 2019), transitioning to clean energy sources, such as hydrogen, is imperative to meet carbon mitigation targets and reduce reliance on fossil fuels. Implementing strategies prioritizing energy efficiency, using district energy systems, and integrating renewable energy production within a specific area are essential for attaining carbon neutrality by 2050. In addition, the creation of regional hydrogen clusters may promote cooperation and ingenuity in hydrogen and fuel cell technologies, so enhancing the potential for hydrogen to be a sustainable energy option that is both scalable and feasible. Adopting hydrogen as a crucial element of the energy combination shows potential in tackling environmental issues, stimulating economic growth, and improving the general standard of living in a society with limited carbon emissions.

Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Ahad, M. T., Bhuiyan, M. M., Sakib, A. N., Becerril Corral, A., & Siddique, Z. (2022). An Overview of Challenges for the Future of Hydrogen. *Materials*, 16(20), 6680. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma16206680>
- Ali, M., Sultana, R., Tahir, S., Watson, I. A., & Saleem, M. (2017). Prospects of microalgal biodiesel production in Pakistan – A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 80, 1588-1596. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.08.062>
- Amin, M., Shah, H. H., Fareed, A. G., Khan, W. U., Chung, E., Zia, A., Rahman Farooqi, Z. U., & Lee, C. (2022). Hydrogen production through renewable and non-renewable energy processes and their impact on climate change. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 47(77), 33112-33134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2022.07.172>
- Arroyo, V. (2019). Examining How Federal Infrastructure Policy Could Help Mitigate and Adapt to Climate Change: Hearing Before the H. Comm. on Transp. & Infrastructure, 116th Cong., Georgetown University Law Center. Retrieved from <https://scholarship.law.georgetown.edu/cong/125>
- Beiron, J., Normann, F., & Johnsson, F. (2022). A techno-economic assessment of CO₂ capture in biomass and waste-fired combined heat and power plants – A Swedish case study¹. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, 116, 103684. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJGGC.2022.103684>
- Blank, L., Cady, T., Cox, K., Murray, R., Savage, R. L., Williams, R. D. (1973). *A hydrogen energy carrier. Volume 2: Systems analysis*. University of Houston, NASA-Johnson Space Center, Rice University. Retrieved from <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/search.jsp?R=19740003615>
- Boogaard, H., Patton, A., Atkinson, R., Brook, J., Chang, H., Crouse, D., Fussell, J., Hoek, G., Hoffmann, B., Kappeler, R., Kutlar Joss, M., Ondras, M., Sagiv, S., Samoli, E., Shaikh, R., Smargiassi, A., Szpiro, A., Van Vliet, E.,

- Vienneau, D., . . . Forastiere, F. (2022). Long-term exposure to traffic-related air pollution and selected health outcomes: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Environment International*, 164, 107262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2022.107262>
- Dawood, F., Anda, M., & Shafiullah, G. (2020). Hydrogen production for energy: An overview. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 45(7), 3847-3869. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.12.059>
- Demuyneck, J., De Paepe, M., Huisseune, H., Sierens, R., Vancoillie, J., & Verhelst, S. (2010). On the applicability of empirical heat transfer models for hydrogen combustion engines. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 36(1), 975-984. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2010.10.059>
- Dogger, J.W., Erisman, J.W., Hazel, P.J., van den, Heederik, D.J.J., Leemans, R., Legler, J., Passchier, W.F., Sluijs, J.P. (2009). Hydrogen-powered Road vehicles: The health benefits and drawbacks of a new fuel. Health Council of the Netherlands. Horizon-scanning report. Retrieved from <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/29251516.pdf>
- Egenhofer, C., Milford, L., Fujiwara, N., Brewer, T. L., & Alessi, M. (2007). Low-Carbon Technologies in the Post-Bali Period: Accelerating their Development and Deployment (ECP Report No. 4). European Climate Platform (ECP). Retrieved from <https://core.ac.uk/download/5081964.pdf>
- Falcone, P. M., Hiete, M., & Sapio, A. (2021). Hydrogen economy and sustainable development goals: Review and policy insights. *Current Opinion in Green and Sustainable Chemistry*, 31, 100506. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogsc.2021.100506>
- Gao, N., Kamran, K., Quan, C., & Williams, P. T. (2020). Thermochemical conversion of sewage sludge: A critical review. *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science*, 79, 100843. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pecs.2020.100843>
- Hacking, N., Pearson, P., & Eames, M. (2019). Mapping innovation and diffusion of hydrogen fuel cell technologies: Evidence from the UK's hydrogen fuel cell technological innovation system, 1954–2012. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 44(57), 29805–29848. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.09.137>
- Hannum, N. P. (1989). Technology Issues Associated With Fueling the National Aerospace Plane With Slush Hydrogen (NASA Technical Memorandum 101386). Retrieved from <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/search.jsp?R=19890000752>
- Hassan, M., Zavareh, D., & Ricci, S. (2019). *Assessment of energy and emissions saving solutions in urban rail-based transport systems*. Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Railway Operations Modelling and Analysis - RailNorrköping 2019. Sapienza Università di Roma - DICEA. Retrieved from <https://core.ac.uk/download/231748963.pdf>
- Hosseini, S. E. (2023). Hydrogen fuel, a game changer for the world's energy scenario. *International Journal of Green Energy*, 21(6), 1366–1382. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15435075.2023.2244050>
- Inayat, A., Ahmad, M. M., Mutalib, M. I. A., Yusup, S., & Khan, Z. (2017). Economic analysis and optimization for bio-hydrogen production from oil palm waste via steam gasification. *Energy Sources, Part B: Economics, Planning, and Policy*, 12(2), 158–165. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15567249.2014.937881>
- Iulianelli A., & Basile A. (2014). *Advances in Hydrogen Production, Storage and Distribution*. Elsevier.
- Jamasb, T., Nuttall, W. J., & Pollitt, M. G. (2006). New Electricity Technologies for a Sustainable Future. <https://doi.org/10.17863/CAM.5458>
- Kabeyi, M. J., & Olanrewaju, O. A. (2022). Sustainable Energy Transition for Renewable and Low Carbon Grid Electricity Generation and Supply. *Frontiers in Energy Research*, 9, 743114. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2021.743114>
- Khan, A. (2023). Implementation of Industry 4.0 in the development of the Space Industry12.

- Bachelor's Thesis, AE1049, Bachelor's Degree in Business Administration. Retrieved from <https://core.ac.uk/download/570977778.pdf>
- Lebrouhi, B., Djoupo, J., Lamrani, B., Benabdelaziz, K., & Kousksou, T. (2022). Global hydrogen development - A technological and geopolitical overview. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 47(11), 7016-7048. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2021.12.076>
- Manuel, J., Serrano, J., Pinzi, S., José, F., & Dorado, M. P. (2023). A Review of the Use of Hydrogen in Compression Ignition Engines with Dual-Fuel Technology and Techniques for Reducing NOx Emissions. *Sustainability*, 16(8), 3462. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16083462>
- Megia, P. J., Vizcaíno, A. J., Calles, J. A., & Carrero, A. (2021). Hydrogen Production Technologies: From Fossil Fuels toward Renewable Sources1. A Mini Review. *Energy Fuels*, 35(20), 16403–16415. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.energyfuels.1c02501>
- Moretto, P., & Quong, S. (2021). Legal requirements, technical regulations, codes, and standards for hydrogen safety. *Hydrogen Safety for Energy Applications*, 345-396. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-820492-4.00003-8>
- Navarro, J. C., Centeno, M. A., Laguna, O. H., & Odriozola, J. A. (2018). Policies and Motivations for the CO₂ Valorization through the Sabatier Reaction Using Structured Catalysts. *A Review of the Most Recent Advances. Catalysts*, 8(578), 1-25. <https://doi.org/10.3390/catal8120578>
- Neves, S. A., Marques, A. C., & Patrício, M. (2020). Determinants of CO₂ emissions in European Union countries: Does environmental regulation reduce environmental pollution? *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 68, 114-125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eap.2020.09.005>
- Qadir, S. A., Al-Motairi, H., Tahir, F., & Al-Fagih, L. (2021). Incentives and strategies for financing the renewable energy transition: A review. *Energy Reports*, 7, 3590-3606. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyr.2021.06.041>
- Romm J. J. (2013). *The Hype About Hydrogen*. Island Press.
- Sikiru, S., Oladosu, T. L., Amosa, T. I., Olutoki, J. O., Ansari, M., Abioye, K. J., Rehman, Z. U., & Soleimani, H. (2024). Hydrogen-powered horizons: Transformative technologies in clean energy generation, distribution, and storage for sustainable innovation. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 56, 1152-1182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.12.186>
- Singla, M.K., Nijhawan, P. & Oberoi, A.S. (2021). Hydrogen fuel and fuel cell technology for cleaner future: a review. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28, 15607-15626. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-12231-8>
- Soto, A. (2021). Carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) and how to accelerate the development and commercialization of carbon base products in the European and US market (Doctoral dissertation, Politecnico di Torino)12. <http://www.politodiotorino.it/11583/2942140>
- Speers, P., & Walsh, C. (2010). A Hydrogen Framework for the East Midlands. CENEX. Nottingham Trent University, emda Knowledge Bank. Retrieved from <https://core.ac.uk/download/30624505.pdf>
- Stickles, R. P., & Breuer, C. T. (1983). New applications for phosphoric acid fuel cells. NASA Report NASA-CR-16820. Retrieved from <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/search.jsp?R=19840010689>
- Terlouw, T., Bauer, C., Rosa, L., & Mazzotti, M. (2021). A critical review on conducted Life Cycle Assessments (LCAs) of a comprehensive set of CDR technologies1. *Energy & Environmental Science*, 14, 1701-1721. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0EE03757E>
- Walsh, M. J., Fox-Penner, P., Zheng, K., Pollack, A., & Cleveland, C. J. (2019). Carbon Free Boston: Energy Technical Report (Boston University Institute for Sustainable Energy, Boston, MA, USA). Retrieved from <https://hdl.handle.net/2144/39216>